

Local Awareness and Satisfaction on Sustainable Projects for People with Disabilities

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Abstract

Purpose: The research aimed to determine various sustainable projects offered by various institutions for people with disabilities (PWDs) in Oman; to analyse the local community's awareness of those projects and their satisfaction with the provided facilities and services to PWDs and to assess the relationship between awareness and satisfaction with the services provided to PWDs.

Design/methodology/approach: This study adopted a descriptive research design and a mixed approach. Primary data were obtained through a survey questionnaire and interview. Snowball sampling was employed with a total of 60 respondents from local communities, people living with disabled people, and institutions catering to the needs of people with disabilities.

Findings: The findings showed that the majority of the population was highly aware of the education programs, access services, employment, and healthcare provided to people with disabilities. An overall high satisfaction rating was obtained for the provided facilities' accessibility and services. Furthermore, results indicated no significant association between age groups and participants' awareness and satisfaction towards facilities accessibility as well as services provided to PWDs. The outcomes likewise revealed a significant moderate, positive correlation between awareness and satisfaction with the services made available for PWDs.

Research limitations/implications: The Government of Oman, non-governmental organizations, civil society, and PWDs immensely benefit from this study. This also outlines numerous sustainable initiatives and assessments on the quality of services according to their requirements. This study supports greater community inclusion and participation by PWDs, improving their overall quality of life.

Social Implications: This study highlights the gaps and challenges faced in the implementation of projects that may require attention and improvement. This study also raises more awareness in the community about the difficulties experienced by PWDs and the significance of offering them long-term support.

Originality / Value: This research study explored the local awareness and satisfaction with available sustainable projects for PWDs in Oman. This also outlines the identification of better strategies and approaches in the implementation of sustainable programs and policy development for people with disabilities among various institutions and the Government of Oman.

Keywords: People with Disabilities, Local Community, Sustainable Projects, Local Community's Satisfaction, Local Community's Awareness.

Introduction

Disability rights advocates have drawn society's focus to the multiple social, cultural, economic, and political obstacles encountered by numerous individuals with impairments. These movements have obtained increasing support for disabled individuals globally, and various initiatives have impacted government disability policies ([Federal Register of Legislation, 2023](#)).

The vast majority of the global population affected by disabilities, numbering over one billion, reside in low-income and middle-income nations (Banks et al., 2017). Functionally limited individuals are frequently categorized as disabled which results in being denied access to public services, jobs, and education (Al Shaibany, 2010). Due to increased vulnerability to disease, hunger, dangerous living, and working circumstances, and poverty, this exclusion might result in increased impairment (Elwan, 1999; Yeo & Moore, 2003). Every day, marginalization and prejudice are experienced by PWDs. One of the vital aspects on which society should concentrate is local awareness and satisfaction with sustainable projects for people with disabilities (PWDs).

One of the major challenges experienced by PWDs is the high cost of mandatory equipment and the difficulty of accessing them (Guibert, 2019). Globally, numerous PWDs belong to middle-income and low-income families thus, incorporating them into sustainable initiatives is crucial. The goal is to assist all PWDs to achieve their highest level of sustainable independence and become responsible members of society as stipulated by the mission of the Disability Resource Centre (DRC), which aims to build a world where all PWDs are respected, and treated with dignity, and integrated into society (DRC, 2021). Hence, the primary focus of the study was raising awareness and satisfaction of the local community on sustainable projects for PWDs.

The Sultanate of Oman, a rapidly growing Middle Eastern nation now classified as a middle-income country, has undertaken several projects aimed at empowering individuals living with disabilities for a better present and future (UNESCO, 2021). The Ministry of Social Development in Oman plays a pivotal role in initiating these development projects and collaborates with other key ministries such as health and education to ensure sustainable development. The country has witnessed an increased awareness of sustainable projects for individuals with disabilities. The overall success of these projects in Oman is evident through increased employment opportunities, positive educational outcomes, and improved accessibility, showcasing a commitment to sustainable development for PWDs. The enacted disability law in Oman protects discrimination and mandates reasonable accommodations in public spaces, including ramps and lifts. Most buildings in Oman, including government structures, hospitals, and shopping malls, are equipped with lifts for PWDs, reflecting a commitment to human rights and equal access.

Employment of disabled individuals in Oman's Government reflects successful initiatives promoting skills gained through special needs education (Times News Service, 2019). The Ministry of Education in Oman offers special needs education for children living with disabilities (UNESCO, 2021). The Ministry of Social Development in Oman spearheads a special needs education project, addressing the inequality gap by providing education to children with various disabilities. Special needs education is offered in specialized schools such as Al-Amal for the deaf and Omar bin Al-Khattab for the blind. This specialized education targets closing the inequality gap faced by children with disabilities, providing them with essential skills for enhanced life opportunities and employment. The emphasis on special needs education has equipped individuals with disabilities with the necessary skills to contribute meaningfully to the workforce. This rise in employment signifies the success of educational initiatives in Oman, particularly those catering to PWDs.

Problem Statement

UNICEF (2020) reported that approximately 10,880 children in Oman live with disabilities. UNICEF noted that half of the population aged 5-17 years has enrolled in special needs education. Inclusive education initiatives, launched in 2005-2006, have seen public schools adopt inclusive educational programs (UNESCO, 2021). UNESCO notes that while three public schools specialize in catering to students with disabilities, increased awareness among parents has led to a decline in enrolled students in these schools, emphasizing the preference for integrating children into primary education schools. Further to that, the country has also implemented policies and programs focused on providing access to healthcare, education, and employment for PWDs, with organizations offering support to individuals and their families. However, PWDs experience more difficulties and the implications of offering require long-term support for them as challenges persist in ensuring equal access to healthcare and other services. This was the reason for the reason study.

Research Questions

- What are the available sustainable projects for PWDs in Oman?
- How aware is the local community of these projects as well as the facilities and services provided to PWDs?
- Does age group influence participant's awareness and satisfaction with the services and facilities provided to PWDs?
- What is the extent of the relationship between awareness and satisfaction with the services provided to PWDs?

Research Objectives

- To determine various sustainable projects for PWDs in Oman
- To assess the local community's awareness of the different projects provided to PWDs
- To determine the association between age groups and participants' awareness as well as satisfaction with the services and facilities accessibility provided to PWDs
- To assess the relationship between awareness and satisfaction with the services provided to PWDs.

Literature Review

Disability laws in Oman

Oman has implemented crucial laws and regulations under the Royal Decree No. 63/2008 to safeguard the rights of individuals with disabilities towards rehabilitation ([Ministry of Social Development](#), 2008). A national committee, established for the same, focuses on evaluating the conditions of children with disabilities ([Times News Service](#), 2019; [UNICEF](#), 2019). This committee not only formulates plans for the care, employment, and advancement of the disabled but also plays a vital role in raising awareness about various disabilities and preventive measures ([Ministry of Social Development](#), 2008; [ONA](#), 2019).

The Government of Oman is committed to providing treatment and healthcare services for disabled individuals, along with facilitating access to equipment essential for mobility, education, training, and daily activities, including rehabilitation devices ([Alqaryouti](#), 2010). [Guidry-Grimes et al.](#) (2020) emphasized the significance of disability rights, proposing practical approaches for standardized care, and have advocated for fair treatment, equitable processes, engagement, enrollment in special needs education, and interactive communication for individuals with disabilities.

Emphasizing the involvement of disabled individuals in decision-making processes leads to more sustainable and successful initiatives. Inclusive participation of people with disabilities is deemed vital in Oman, as evidenced by [Alqaryouti](#), (2010). To enhance inclusivity, it has been recommended that companies, both private and public, should employ a minimum of two individuals with disabilities. This approach aims to reduce unemployment among individuals with disabilities and foster collaboration as PWDs are viewed not as burdens but as productive community members capable of contributing positively to society ([Faraj](#), 2016).

Sustainable Projects for PWDs

[Association for Project Management](#) (2020) highlighted the integration of environmental, social, and economic aspects in project-based work while proposing the concept of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and sustainability. CSR project named 'Saksham' is a campaign in India supporting PWDs in their livelihood apart from receiving assistive technology ([Fernandes](#), 2020). [Peterson](#) (2021) investigated the accessibility to buildings by PWDs through the presence of essential elements like ramps and elevators and concluded that the government was actively working on enhancing accessibility. The Ministry of Social Development also focuses on promoting accessibility to buildings for PWDs, aligning with a strategic plan that covers infrastructure, public transportation, and tourism, ensuring equal access for impaired individuals ([Muscat Daily](#), 2023). [WHO](#) (2023) emphasizes the importance of such accessibility measures, ensuring they contribute to a more inclusive society for all individuals, both now and in the future.

Oman has embarked on innovative projects for PWDs aligning with sustainable development goals particularly in education and access to infrastructure ([Lalit](#), 2021). [Mustafa & Aldein](#) (2020) evaluated the autistic education of children with disabilities in Oman and revealed that social interaction impairment

significantly affected autistic children, emphasizing the need for increased attention from educators and the immediate community (Alshar'e & Mustafa, 2021). Al-Hadabi et al. (2021) explored the impact of physical education on the attitudes of PWDs toward sports in Oman, noting positive modifications in students' perspectives.

Institutions' Initiatives for Local community's awareness of projects for PWDs

Oman has made notable progress by being among the first in the Arab region to advocate for the integration of children with special needs into education, indicating community awareness and the potential for further service expansion (UNICEF, 2020). Despite advancements in healthcare for PWDs in Oman, WHO (2023) emphasized the need for continued efforts. Human Rights Watch (2020) highlighted the stigma associated with children with disabilities, leading parents and guardians to refrain from registering their children in initiated projects. Increased awareness among parents about available projects and services is crucial. Faraj (2016) pointed out that the challenges in accessing rehabilitation services are primarily concentrated in urban areas due to high setup costs and a shortage of trained teachers and social workers for early intervention.

United Nations (2019) report stipulated disability inclusion in the workplace and companies' acknowledgment of implementing inclusive policies and reasonable accommodations for employees with disabilities. OHCHR (2018) emphasized the rights of PWDs viz. protection from discrimination and the implementation of a new penal code safeguarding individuals, especially girls from sexual abuse and honor crimes. The Ministry of Social Development highlighted the adoption of universal design principles by many businesses to ensure accessibility and usability for individuals with diverse abilities, suggesting that businesses in Oman are increasingly recognizing the benefits of diversity, including the employment of PWDs (ONA, 2022).

Local Community's Satisfaction with Projects/Services for PWDs

Al-Ani et al. (2020) indicated positive attitudes among students, with technology aiding information search, idea sharing, collaboration, and acting as a motivational tool for learning. Mustafa & Aldein (2020) studied the impact of e-learning on autistic students and highlighted the challenges related to teacher shortages affecting social interaction. Al-Yahyai et al. (2021) & Al-Hadabi et al. (2021) delved into the positive effects of art education on learners' attitudes, showcasing improved attitudes and a sense of achievement among participants.

The Ministry of Health (MOH) in Oman has been working towards comprehensive healthcare services for PWDs, including specialized clinics and rehabilitation centers though efforts have also been directed towards improving accessibility and inclusivity in healthcare facilities. Still, effectiveness may vary across regions (MOH, 2023). Promoting accessibility to buildings and transportation, the efforts of the Omani accessibility initiative have ensured installations such as lifts and elevators in various buildings (Ministry of Social Development, 2008). The disability law in Oman mandates equal access to education, infrastructure, and employment, with regulations requiring buildings to include better access services. Javid et al. (2021) revealed that crossing facility designs for pedestrians in Oman for PWDs significantly reduced accidents. Progress has been made in improving accessibility and parking for disabled individuals in public places though continuous improvement is advocated (Yousuf, 2021). Further, initiatives by the Kaderoon Forum have been made to train, rehabilitate, and employ PWDs to combat begging and contribute to their psychological well-being (Zawya Press Release, 2019).

The Government of Oman is actively engaged in providing comprehensive healthcare services for PWDs, which includes the establishment of specialized clinics and rehabilitation centers (MOH, 2023). The Ministry of Social Development in Oman is instrumental in promoting accessibility to buildings and transportation to facilitate PWDs' seamless access to services and facilities (Ministry of Social Development, 2008). Javid et al. (2021) highlight those pedestrians in Oman, particularly People with Disabilities, prioritize safety when crossing roads. This focus on safety is attributed to well-designed facilities, resulting in a reduction in accidents. The commitment to safety underscores the positive impact of infrastructure improvements.

Underpinned by disability laws in Oman there is a firm commitment to ensuring equal access for all individuals to education, infrastructure, and employment opportunities (ONA, 2019). Employment opportunities for disabled individuals in the Omani Government experienced an 18 percent increase, as reported by the National Center for Statistics and Information (Omar et al., 2021).

Improvements in Sustainable Projects

[Al-Ani et al.](#) (2020) recommended that training should be provided to teachers unfamiliar with the benefits of assistive technology for students with learning disabilities which prevents the potential negative impact of the technology on student learning and the critical factor, was the need for a universal learning design. In contrast, [Al-Yahyai et al.](#) (2021) & [Al-Hadabi et al.](#) (2021), recommended making special art courses core by increasing teaching hours, specifically advocating for the inclusion of autism education as part of the curriculum. Furthermore, it was suggested that admitting more students with disabilities to these courses would contribute positively to the overall attitude of the students and enhance the dissemination of artistic education to special groups ([Mustafa & Aldein](#), 2020). [Al-Ani et al.](#) (2020) and [Al-Yahyai et al.](#) (2021) recommended that autistic children require educational tools and materials designed to meet their unique needs, underscoring the importance of special care and support for this particular group to facilitate their contribution to the community. In alignment with these recommendations, [Javid et al.](#) (2021) suggested that road designs should focus on pedestrian behavior at crossings, both with and without signals, emphasizing the importance of designing road infrastructure with pedestrians, including those with disabilities, in mind.

Hypotheses

Based on the review of the literature, the following hypotheses were drawn:

H1: There is a significant association between age groups and participants' awareness of available services provided to PWDs.

H2: There is a significant relationship between age groups and respondents' satisfaction with Facilities Accessibility.

H3: There is a significant association between age groups and participants' satisfaction with available services offered to PWDs.

H4: There is a correlation between awareness and satisfaction with services provided to PWDs.

Research Methodology

The research employed a mixed approach involving a survey questionnaire and interview for data collection ([Aspers & Corte](#), 2019). A quantitative approach involving a research design was employed where an investigation on the level of awareness and satisfaction was conducted on the available sustainable projects for PWDs in Oman. A qualitative approach in the form of an interview was also carried out to determine various projects and activities provided by institutions to PWDs in Oman ([Barrett & Twycross](#), 2018). The target population was local people with disabilities and PWDs registered in institutions providing services to society ([Ackerman et al.](#), 2019). Sixty samples were drawn from the population employing snowball or referral sampling techniques ([Parker et al.](#), 2019). JASP software was employed in analyzing statistical techniques through the collected data as [Mishra et al.](#) (2019) considered it was easy and apt. The non-parametric tests such as Chi-Squared Test and Spearman's Correlation were conducted to analyze respondents' awareness and satisfaction with the services provided to PWDs. Data were summarized in tables indicating the results of appropriate tests conducted to achieve presented objectives and hypotheses validation.

Interviewed Institution: Designated authorities from Oman Sail - which is one of the institutions formed to provide windsurfing and diving activities to people with disabilities. The organization has seen an increase in the amount of people looking for the services as a form of recreation and occupational/physical therapy. Oman Sail program has been successful in providing sailing, diving, and windsurfing activities to the community, including PWDs.

Findings
Demographic profile

Table 1. Demographic Profile

		Freq	%
Gender	Male	26	43.0
	Female	34	57.0
Nationality	Omani	59	98.0
	Non-Omani	1	2.0
Age	16-20	5	8.0
	21-25	32	52.0
	26-30	20	33.0
	Above 31	4	7.0

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of sixty individuals who participated in the study.

Provision of Projects to People with Disabilities

Table 2. Importance of Project Provision

	Very important	Important	Neutral	Slightly important	Unimportant	Mean	Verbal interpretation
Level of importance to provide projects for people with disabilities	48%	13%	10%	12%	17%	2.35	High level of importance

Table 2 highlights the importance of advocating greater accessibility and inclusion for PWDs. The overall result indicated high importance (M=2.35) for sustainable project provision to PWDs.

Table 3. Awareness of Programs for PWDs

	Education program	Access services	Employment	Health care services	overall mean-awareness
Mean	1.733	1.900	2.050	1.717	1.850
Verbal interpretation	Very High	High	High	Very High	High

The above results indicated in Table 3 revealed that a significant majority of the participants were aware of various programs and services that were designed to provide services and information to PWDs. The overall result showed that most of the respondents (M=1.850) were highly aware of the education programs, access services, employment, and healthcare services provided to PWDs.

H1: There is a significant association between age groups and participants' awareness of available services provided to PWDs

Table 4. Service Awareness

Service Awareness Level		Age Group				Total
		16-20	21-25	26-30	Above 31	
High	Count	3.00	10.00	10.00	3.00	26.00
	% within row	11.54%	38.46%	38.46%	11.54%	100%
Moderate	Count	0.000	3.000	3.000	0.00	6.000
	% within row	0.00 %	50.00%	50.00 %	0.00%	100 %
Very High	Count	2.00	18.00	7.00	1.00	28.00
	% within row	7.14 %	64.29 %	25.00 %	3.57%	100%
Total	Count	5.00	31.00	20.00	4.00	60.00
	% within row	8.33%	51.67%	33.33%	6.67%	100%

Chi-squared Tests

	Value	df	p
Chi-square	5.628	6	0.466
N	60		

A chi-square test presented in Table 4 was performed to find out if there is a significant association between age groups and participant's awareness of various services provided to PWDs. Table 4 indicated no significant association between age groups with awareness $\chi^2(6, N=60) = 5.63, p=0.466$.

Satisfaction on Facilities Accessibility for PWDs

Table 5. Satisfaction with Facilities Accessibility

	Accessibility to the buildings and government facilities	Crossing facilities	Non-governmental rehabilitation centers	Schools	Parking	Overall mean-facilities
Mean	2.033	2.567	2.217	2.117	1.717	2.130
Satisfaction verbal interpretation	High	High	High	High	Very High	High

Table 5 presents data showing participants' satisfaction with access to various facilities in Oman. Accessibility to the buildings and government facilities (M= 2.033) indicates respondents' high satisfaction with government facilities access, which is critical in providing various services to individuals. Crossing facilities (M=2.567), non-governmental rehabilitation centers (M= 2.217), and schools (M= 2.117) indicated a high level of satisfaction among respondents. Parking facilities (M=1.717) solely indicated a very high satisfaction among respondents. An overall rating (M=2.130) was presented denoting PWDs' highly satisfied quality of life in Oman.

H2: There is a significant relationship between age groups and respondents' satisfaction with Facilities Accessibility

Table 6. Facilities Accessibility Satisfaction using Chi-Square Test

Facilities Accessibility Satisfaction Level		Age Group				Total
		16-20	21-25	26-30	Above 31	
Low	Count	0.00	1.00	2.00	1.00	4.00
	% within row	0%	25.00%	50.00%	25.00%	100%
High	Count	1.00	19.00	7.00	2.00	29.00
	% within row	3.45%	65.51%	24.14%	6.90%	100%
Moderate	Count	1.000	5.00	6.00	1.00	13.00
	% within row	7.69 %	38.46 %	46.15 %	7.70%	100%
Very High	Count	3.00	6.00	5.00	0.00	14.00
	% within row	21.43 %	2.86 %	35.71 %	0%	100%
Total	Count	5.00	31.00	20.00	4.00	60.00
	% within row	8.33%	51.67%	33.33%	6.67%	100%

Chi-squared Tests

	Value	df	p
Chi-square	11.034	9	0.273
N	60		

A chi-square test of independence shown in Table 8 was likewise employed indicating no significant association between age groups and satisfaction level of participants to facilities accessibility, $\chi^2(9, N=60)$ is 11.03, $p=0.273$.

Table 7. Satisfaction with Available Services

	Education	Employment	Health care	Vocational training	Overall mean-services
Mean	1.650	2.383	1.783	2.267	2.021
Verbal Interpretation	Very High	High	Very High	High	High

Table 7 above shows the mean ratings of education ($M=1.650$) and Health care ($M=1.783$) indicating 'Very High' satisfaction with available services for PWDs whereas, Employment ($M=2.383$) and Vocational training ($M=2.267$) reflected a high level of satisfaction. An overall rating ($M=2.021$) indicated PWDs' high satisfaction with available services.

H3: There is a significant association between age groups and satisfaction with available services offered to PWDs

Table 8. Service Satisfaction Using Chi-Square Test

Service Satisfaction Level		Age Group				Total
		16-20	21-25	26-30	Above 31	
Low	Count	0.00	0.00	2.00	0.00	2.00
	% within row	0%	0%	100.00%	0%	100%
High	Count	2.00	16.00	7.00	4.00	29.00
	% within row	6.90%	55.17%	24.14%	13.79%	100%
Moderate	Count	0.00	3.00	3.00	0.00	6.00
	% within row	0%	50.00%	50.00%	0%	100%
Very High	Count	3.00	12.00	8.00	0.00	23.00
	% within row	13.05%	52.17%	34.78%	0%	100%
Total	Count	5.00	31.00	20.00	4.00	60.00
	% within row	8.33%	51.67%	33.33%	6.67%	100%

Chi-squared Tests

	Value	df	p
Chi-square	10.650	9	0.300
N	60		

A chi-square test of independence as presented in Table 8 revealed no significant association between age groups and satisfaction level of participants, $\chi^2(9, N=60) = 10.65, p = .300$.

H4: There is a correlation between awareness and satisfaction with services provided to PWDs

Table 9. Spearman's Correlations

	n	Spearman's coefficient	p-value
Awareness of Service – Satisfaction with Services	60	0.382**	.003
*p <.05, **p<.01, ***p<.001			

Spearman's correlation was also performed to assess the relationship between awareness and satisfaction with the services provided to PWDs. Table 9 above showed a significant moderate, positive correlation between the two variables, $r(59) = 0.38, p = 0.003$.

Responses about the programs, facilities & Improvements for PWDs

Respondents highlighted the following key suggestions for programs and facilities for PWDs in Oman:

1. Improvements in access facilities and accessibility in some areas.
2. Additional vocational training opportunities and projects/programs.
3. More employment opportunities, development of leadership and programmatic skills, and creating a mutually supportive community for PWDs in both government and private sectors.
4. Presence of rehabilitation centres in various places.

Apart from the above recommendations, participants also stressed the importance of understanding and meeting the specific needs of PWDs. Similarly, emphasis was also placed on the importance of creating a friendly environment for PWDs making them feel confident and valued. These recommendations demonstrated the range of interventions that are needed to support PWDs and improve their quality of life.

Discussion

Sustainable Projects for PWDs

Various sustainable projects such as education, employment, healthcare services, and access to these services play a significant role in enhancing the quality of life among PWDs (Times News Service, 2022 & Times News Service, 2023). The above results revealed that most of the respondents believed that providing projects for PWDs was very essential, indicating a strong emphasis on the need to support and empower PWDs in society.

Educational programs and key facilities currently offered in the country were assessed and were found to be easily accessible (United Nations, 2019). Access to Governmental and civilian services was also made available to the public. An investigation was likewise focused on determining the number of individuals employed in the country and how these employment programs impact the population. Ultimately, the healthcare sector is involved in receiving critical care services aimed at preventing or reducing the harm of disease, access to medication, and care services in healthcare settings.

Table 10. Summary of the Interview Responses

Designation	Initiative aims	Observations	Suggestions
Managers, Oman Sail	Oman Sail's various programs and facilities help to provide services aimed at improving the quality of life for PWDs.	1. The unfavorable notions towards the organized activities for PWDs among their families. There was reluctance to allow members to participate in such activities.	There is a need for more awareness campaigns among the local community about the benefits of sustainable projects for PWDs.
		2. There was evidence of successful implementation of the program as well as high turnouts of participants since it began. However, there are still residents who have unfavorable opinions about the initiatives.	
		3. Institutions' success correlated with the importance of investing in sustainable projects for PWDs.	

Awareness of the local community on the different projects provided to PWDs

One of the study's objectives was to determine the local community's level of awareness of the different projects provided to PWDs. The research findings showed that the majority of the population was aware of the services provided to PWDs. However, the results were merely indicative of the participants' awareness of these projects and services' existence.

Previous studies reflected the country taking various measures to increase awareness of sustainable projects for PWDs. Measures were taken to protect individuals from discrimination and rehabilitation services expanded reaching out to individuals with disabilities (OHCHR, 2018). This aligns with the report from the World Health Organization (WHO) on the efforts of the country to improve various programs, especially in healthcare, for PWDs. The findings also showed an overall 'high' awareness of healthcare services, education

programs, access to services, and employment programs among respondents. This is a good indicator that current initiatives gained a positive impact.

Satisfaction of the local community on the Sustainable project for PWDs

One of the objectives aimed at determining whether the programs were efficiently addressing the needs of PWDs in Oman. Respondents provided critical information to determine their satisfaction with the current programs' implementation and to identify areas for improvement. There were two main areas viz, facilities and services which were assessed measuring the level of participants' satisfaction. Parameters under facilities include buildings and government facilities accessibility, crossing facilities, non-governmental rehabilitation centers, schools, and parking while education, employment, health care, and vocational training were the categories incorporated under services. The overall findings showed that the local community was highly satisfied with both the facilities and services provided for PWDs.

Association between Age Groups and Awareness as well as Satisfaction towards Services and Facilities Accessibility for PWDs

The results revealed that no significant association between age groups and awareness in addition to satisfaction with the services and facilities accessibility for PWDs. This is a clear indication that participants' ages do not influence the extent of awareness and satisfaction among the respondents.

Awareness and Satisfaction Association on Services for PWDs

The findings showed a moderate, positive correlation between participants' awareness and satisfaction with services provided to PWDs. This was also indicated in the overall results obtaining a high level of both awareness and satisfaction.

Conclusion

The study aimed to identify current sustainable projects and determine participants' awareness and satisfaction with the facilities and services provided for PWDs. The overall findings indicated that there were positive and high levels of awareness and satisfaction among respondents. It was highly recommended that private and public stakeholders cooperate in program enhancement and improving the quality of life amongst PWDs. Some of the recommended approaches include improving access to services, employment, access to health care services, and access to educational programs. Based on the findings, it was evident that such programs have positive impacts on the communities, thereby giving room to further research affecting PWDs and identifying appropriate solutions to challenges currently experienced. To summarize, it can be said that the study indicates that the programs were effectively implemented addressing the requirements of the local community.

Recommendations

Several recommendations were provided for improving the facilities and services of available sustainable projects for PWDs. The importance of PWDs' inclusion in Government and private sectors, developing leadership and programmatic skills, and creating a mutually supportive community was emphasized. Additionally, the recommendations reflected considerations on addressing PWDs' specific needs as well as making them feel valued and important.

On the other hand, despite findings exhibiting a high level of satisfaction among respondents in terms of programs facilities, and services, there was still a need to improve access to Government facilities and non-governmental rehabilitation facilities with consideration to safety and security.

Sustainable projects for PWDs posed a positive impact on the quality of life of PWDs and contributed to a more inclusive and accessible society. Organizing awareness campaign activities as well as addressing challenges for individuals can be made better and more extensive participation among community members.

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